

TOPOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF SILICON CARBIDE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Topological indices enable information about the underlying topology of chemical and physical substances. Topological indices are grouped into two categories; degree based and distance based. Degree based topological indices are defined by using classical degree concept in graph theory. Ev-degree and ve-degree which have been defined recently are two novel degree concepts in graph theory. Also Ev-degree and ve-degree based topological indices have been defined as parallel to corresponding classical degree based topological indices. Molecular classical degree based topological properties of silicon carbon structures have been investigated recently. In this study we investigate ev-degree and ve-degree molecular topological properties of two silicon carbon structures of Si_2C_3 -I and of Si_2C_3 -II.

Keywords: *Ev-degree topological indices, Ve-degree topological indices, Silicon carbide structures*

MSC: 05C09, 05C07

1. Introduction

Chemical graph theory is one of the important branch of graph theory as a considered the intersection of graph theory, physics, chemistry and information science. Molecular graph are used to represent two dimensional representation of molecular structures. Topological indices are numerical values derived the molecular graphs. Topological indices are necessary tools to acquire the information about the underlying topology of molecular substances.

Carborundum, also known as Silicon carbide which containing carbon and silicon is a semiconductor. Silicon carbide is the hardest of the conventional abrasives, but has lower impact resistance than aluminium oxide and shows a higher wear rate when used for grinding steels. It was originally produced by a high temperature electro-chemical reaction of sand and carbon. Silicon has numerous preferences over other semiconductor materials: It is, of minimal effort, it is nontoxic, essentially its accessibility is boundless, and behind it many years of involvement in purging, development and gadget creation. A novel thermal plasma-based technology for submicronic silicon carbide production at pilot scale investigated in [1]. Stored energy release in neutron irradiated silicon carbide studied in [2]. Silicon carbide diodes in power-factor correction circuits: device and circuit design aspects have been investigated in [3]. Ohmic contacts on n-type and p-type cubic silicon carbide (3C-SiC) grown on silicon have been analyzed in [4]. Grain size variation in nanocrystalline silicon carbide irradiated at elevated temperatures were studied in [5].

Self-crack healing ability and strength recovery in ytterbium disilicate/silicon carbide nanocomposites have been analyzed in [6]. Influence of topological constraints on ion damage resistance of amorphous hydrogenated silicon carbide was studied in [7]. All-dielectric radar absorbing array metamaterial based on silicon carbide/carbon foam material has been investigated in [8]. Silicon carbide nanowire field effect transistors with high on/off current ratio was investigated in [9]. Other electronic, physical and ceramic properties of silicon carbide, we refer the interested reader to the references in [1-9].

Molecular classical degree based topological properties of silicon carbon structures have been investigated recently in [10]. The authors general Randic, Zagreb types indices, geometric arithmetic index, atom–bond connectivity index, fourth atom–bond connectivity and fifth geometric arithmetic index of $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$ and $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$. As a continuation of this study, generalized first and multiplicative Zagreb indices, the multiplicative version of the atomic bondconnectivity index, and the generalized multiplicative geometric arithmetic index of $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$ and $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$ have been investigated in [11]. Novel ev -degree and ve -degree concepts were defined in [12]. And novel ev -degree and ve -degree topological indices have been defined in [13-16].

The aim of this study to investigate novel ev -degree and ve -degree topological properties of $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$ and $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$.

2. Preliminaries

In this section we give some basic and preliminary concepts which we shall use later. A graph $G=(V,E)$ consists of two nonempty sets V and 2-element subsets of V namely E . The elements of V are called vertices and the elements of E are called edges. For a vertex v , $deg(v)$ show the number of edges that incident to v . The set of all vertices which adjacent to v is called the open neighborhood of v and denoted by $N(v)$. If we add the vertex v to $N(v)$, then we get the closed neighborhood of v , $N[v]$.

And now we give the definitions of ev -degree and ve -degree concepts which were given in [12].

Definition 1 (ve-degree) Let G be a connected simple graph and $v \in V(G)$. The ve -degree of the vertex v , $deg_{ve}(v)$, equals the number of different edges that incident to any vertex from the closed neighborhood of v .

We also can restate the Definition 1 as follows: Let G be a connected simple graph and $v \in V(G)$. The ve -degree of the vertex v is the number of different edges between the other vertices with a maximum distance of two from the vertex v .

Definition 2 (ev-degree) Let G be a connected graph and $e=uv \in E(G)$. The ev -degree of the edge e , $deg_{ev}(e)$, equals the number of vertices of the union of the closed neighborhoods of u and v .

The authors in [12] also can give the Definition 2 as follows: Let G be a connected graph and $e=uv \in E(G)$. The ev -degree of the edge e , $deg_{uv}(e)=deg_u+deg_v-n_e$, where n_e means the number of triangles in which the edge e lies in.

Definition 3 (**ev-degree Zagreb index**) Let G be a connected graph and $e=uv \in E(G)$. The ev-degree Zagreb index of the graph G defined as;

$$M^{ev}(G) = \sum_{e \in E(G)} deg_{ev} e^2 (1)$$

Definition 4 (**the first ve-degree Zagreb alpha index**) Let G be a connected graph and $v \in V(G)$. The first ve-degree Zagreb alpha index of the graph G defined as;

$$M_1^{\alpha ve}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} deg_{ve} v^2 (2)$$

Definition 5 (**the first ve-degree Zagreb beta index**) Let G be a connected graph and $uv \in E(G)$. The first ve-degree Zagreb beta index of the graph G defined as;

$$M_1^{\beta ve}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (deg_{ve} u + deg_{ve} v) (3)$$

Definition 6 (**the second ve-degree Zagreb index**) Let G be a connected graph and $uv \in E(G)$. The second ve-degree Zagreb index of the graph G defined as;

$$M_2^{ve}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} deg_{ve} u deg_{ve} v (4)$$

Definition 7 (**ve-degree Randic index**) Let G be a connected graph and $uv \in E(G)$. The ve-degree Randic index of the graph G defined as;

$$R^{ve}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (deg_{ve} u deg_{ve} v)^{-1/2} (5)$$

Definition 8 (**ev-degree Randic index**) Let G be a connected graph and $e=uv \in E(G)$. The ev-degree Randic index of the graph G defined as;

$$R^{ev}(G) = \sum_{e \in E(G)} deg_{ev} e^{-1/2} (6)$$

3. Results

In [10], two dimensional lattices of Si_2C_3 -I[p,q] and Si_2C_3 -II[p,q] were given in the following Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively.

Fig. 1. Two dimensional structure of $Si_2C_3-I[4,2]$

Note that two rows are being connecting, carbon atom C are brown and Silicon atom Si are blue and red lines (edges) connects the upper and lower rows in Fig. 1. $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$ has $10pq$ vertices and $15pq - 2p - 3q$ edges.

Fig. 2. Two dimensional structure of $Si_2C_3-II[5,2]$

Note that, two rows are connecting and green lines (edges) connect the upper and lower rows in Fig.2. Also red lines show the connection between the unit cells in Fig. 2. $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$ has $10pq$ vertices and $15pq - 2p - 3q$ edges.

From the Fig. 1, we give the vertex and edge partition of $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$ with respect to ve-degrees and ev-degrees in the following Tab. 1, Tab. 2. and Tab. 3.

Table 1: Ve-degrees of the $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$

Degree	Ve-degree	Number of vertices
1	3	1
1	4	1
2	4	1
2	5	$3p + 6q - 1$
2	6	$p + 2$
3	5	1
3	7	$p + 2q + 2$
3	8	$2p + 2q - 5$
3	9	$10pq - 7p - 10q - 2$

Table 2: Ev-degrees of the $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$

Edge	Ev-degree	Number of edges
(2,1)	3	1
(3,1)	4	1
(2,2)	4	$p + 2q$
(3,2)	5	$6p + 8q - 14$
(3,3)	6	$15pq - 9p - 13q + 7$

Table 3: Ve-degrees of the end vertices of $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$

Edge	Ve-degrees of end vertices of edge	Number of edges
(2,1)	(4,2)	1
(3,1)	(5,3)	1
(2,2)	(5,5)	$p + 2q$
(3,2)	(5,5)	1
(3,2)	(7,4)	1
(3,2)	(7,5)	$2q + 2$
(3,2)	(5,6)	1
(3,2)	(7,6)	$4p + 2q - 7$
(3,2)	(8,6)	$2q - 2$
(3,2)	(8,5)	$2p + 2q - 5$
(3,3)	(8,7)	1
(3,3)	(8,8)	$p + 2q - 4$
(3,3)	(9,7)	$2p + 2q - 3$
(3,3)	(9,8)	$2p + 4q - 7$
(3,3)	(9,9)	$15pq - 14p - 21q + 20$

From the Fig. 2, we give the vertex and edge partition of $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$ with respect to ve-degrees and ev-degrees in the following Tab. 4. , Tab. 5. and Tab. 6.

Table 4: Ve-degrees of the $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$

Degree	Ve-degree	Number of vertices
1	2	2
1	3	1
2	3	2
2	4	2
2	5	$4p + 4q - 6$
2	6	$2p + 2q - 4$
3	7	$p - 3$
3	8	$4p - 10$
3	9	$10pq - 18p - 12q - 13$

Table 5: Ev-degrees of the $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$

Edge	Ev-degree	Number of edges
(2,1)	3	2
(3,1)	4	1
(2,2)	4	$2p + 2q$
(3,2)	5	$8p + 8q - 14$
(3,3)	6	$15pq - 13p - 13q + 11$

Table 6: Ve-degrees of the end vertices of $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$

Edge	Ve-degrees of end vertices of edge	Number of edges
(2,1)	(3,2)	2
(3,1)	(7,3)	1
(2,2)	(4,3)	2

(2,2)	(5,4)	2
(2,2)	(5,5)	$2p + 2q - 4$
(3,2)	(7,5)	$2p + 2q$
(3,2)	(7,6)	$2p + 2q - 2$
(3,2)	(8,6)	$2p + 2q - 6$
(3,2)	(8,5)	$2p + 2q - 6$
(3,3)	(8,7)	2
(3,3)	(8,8)	$2p + 2q - 8$
(3,3)	(7,7)	2
(3,3)	(9,7)	$2p + 2q - 3$
(3,3)	(9,8)	$2p + 2q - 5$
(3,3)	(9,9)	$15pq - 19p - 19q + 23$

And we begin to compute ev-degree and ve-degree topological indices for $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$.

Theorem 1 The ev-degree and ve-degree topological indices of the $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$ are given in the following table.

Table 7: The topological indices of the $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$

Topological index	Symbol of the topological index	Topological index value of the $Si_2C_3-I[p,q]$
ev-degree Zagreb index	$M^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - I)$	$540pq + 22p - 236q - 81$
the first ve-degree Zagreb alpha index	$M_1^{\alpha ve}(Si_2C_3 - I)$	$810pq - 1001p - 544q - 2067$
the first ve-degree Zagreb beta index	$M_1^{\beta ve}(Si_2C_3 - I)$	$270pq - 120p - 120q + 35$
the second ve-degree Zagreb index	$M_2^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - I)$	$1215pq - 761p - 761q + 721$

ve-degree Randic index	$R^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - I)$	$\frac{15pq - 19p - 19q + 23}{9} + \frac{2p + 2q - 4}{5} + \frac{2p + 2q - 8}{8} + \frac{2p + 2q}{\sqrt{35}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 2}{\sqrt{42}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{4\sqrt{3}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{\sqrt{40}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 3}{\sqrt{63}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 5}{6\sqrt{2}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}}$ $+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$
ev-degree Randic index	$R^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - I)$	$\frac{15pq - 13p - 13q + 11}{\sqrt{6}} + p + q$ $+ \frac{8p + 8q - 14}{\sqrt{5}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{2}$

Proof of Theorem1. From the Figure 1, Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned}
M^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - I) &= \sum_{e \in E(Si_2C_3 - I)} deg_{ev} e^2 \\
&= 1x3^2 + 1x4^2 + (p + 2q)x4^2 + (6p + 8q - 14)x5^2 \\
&+ (15pq - 9p - 13q + 7)x6^2 \\
&= 17 + 16p + 32q + 150p + 200q - 350 + 540pq - 144p - 468q + 252 \\
&= 540pq + 22p - 236q - 81
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1^{\alpha ve}(Si_2C_3 - I) &= \sum_{v \in V(Si_2C_3 - I)} deg_{ve} v^2 \\
&= 2x2^2 + 1x3^2 + 2x3^2 + 2x4^2 + (4p + 4q - 6)x5^2 + (2p + 2q - 4)x6^2 \\
&+ (p - 3)x7^2 + (4p - 10)x8^2 + (10pq - 18p - 12q - 13)x9^2 \\
&= 67 + 100p + 100q - 150 + 72p + 72q - 144 + 49p - 147 + 256p - 640 \\
&+ 810pq - 1458p - 972q - 1053 = 810pq - 1001p - 544q - 2067
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1^{\beta ve}(Si_2C_3 - I) &= \sum_{uv \in E(Si_2C_3 - I)} (deg_{ve} u + deg_{ve} v) \\
&= 2x5 + 1x10 + 2x7 + 2x9 + (2p + 2q - 4)x10 + (2p + 2q)x12 \\
&+ (2p + 2q - 2)x13 + (2p + 2q - 6)x14 + (2p + 2q - 6)x13 + 2x15 \\
&+ (2p + 2q - 8)x16 + 2x14 + (2p + 2q - 3)x16 + (2p + 2q - 5)x17 \\
&+ (15pq - 19p - 19q + 23)x18 = 270pq - 120p - 120q + 35
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_2^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - I) &= \sum_{uv \in E(Si_2C_3 - I)} deg_{ve} u deg_{ve} v \\
&= 2x6 + 1x21 + 2x12 + 2x20 + (2p + 2q - 4)x25 + (2p + 2q)x35 \\
&\quad + (2p + 2q - 2)x42 + (2p + 2q - 6)x48 + (2p + 2q - 6)x40 + 2x56 \\
&\quad + (2p + 2q - 8)x64 + 2x49 + (2p + 2q - 3)x63 + (2p + 2q - 5)x72 \\
&\quad + (15pq - 19p - 19q + 23)x81 = 1215pq - 761p - 761q + 721
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - I) &= \sum_{uv \in E(Si_2C_3 - I)} (deg_{ve} u deg_{ve} v)^{-1/2} \\
&= \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{20}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 4}{\sqrt{25}} + \frac{2p + 2q}{\sqrt{35}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 2}{\sqrt{42}} \\
&\quad + \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{\sqrt{48}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{\sqrt{40}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{56}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 8}{\sqrt{64}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{49}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 3}{\sqrt{63}} \\
&\quad + \frac{2p + 2q - 5}{\sqrt{72}} + \frac{15pq - 19p - 19q + 23}{\sqrt{81}} \\
&= \frac{15pq - 19p - 19q + 23}{9} + \frac{2p + 2q - 4}{5} + \frac{2p + 2q - 8}{8} + \frac{2p + 2q}{\sqrt{35}} \\
&\quad + \frac{2p + 2q - 2}{\sqrt{42}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{4\sqrt{3}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{\sqrt{40}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 3}{\sqrt{63}} + \frac{2p + 2q - 5}{6\sqrt{2}} \\
&\quad + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - I) &= \sum_{e \in E(Si_2C_3 - I)} deg_{ev} e^{-1/2} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} + \frac{2p + 2q}{\sqrt{4}} + \frac{8p + 8q - 14}{\sqrt{5}} \\
&\quad + \frac{15pq - 13p - 13q + 11}{\sqrt{6}} \\
&= \frac{15pq - 13p - 13q + 11}{\sqrt{6}} + p + q + \frac{8p + 8q - 14}{\sqrt{5}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

And now, we begin to compute ev-degree and ve-degree topological indices for $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$.

Theorem 2 The ev-degree and ve-degree topological indices of the $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$ are given in the following table.

Table 8: The topological indices of the $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$

Topological index	Symbol of the topological index	Topological index value of the $Si_2C_3-II[p,q]$
ev-degree Zagreb index	$M^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - II)$	$540pq - 236p - 236q + 80$
the first ve-degree Zagreb alpha index	$M_1^{\alpha ve}(Si_2C_3 - II)$	$810pq - 981p - 800q + 2067$
the first ve-degree Zagreb beta index	$M_1^{\beta ve}(Si_2C_3 - II)$	$270pq - 120p - 120q + 35$

the second ve-degree Zagreb index	$M_2^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - II)$	$1215pq - 761p - 761q + 397$
ve-degree Randic index	$R^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - II)$	$\frac{15pq - 19p - 19q + 23}{9} + \frac{p + q - 4}{2}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 4}{5} + \frac{2p + 2q}{\sqrt{35}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 2}{\sqrt{42}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 4}{4\sqrt{3}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 6}{2\sqrt{10}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 3}{3\sqrt{7}}$ $+ \frac{2p + 2q - 5}{6\sqrt{2}} + \frac{2}{7} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}}$ $+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{14}}$
ev-degree Randic index	$R^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - II)$	$\frac{15pq - 13p - 13q + 11}{\sqrt{6}} + p + q$ $+ \frac{8p + 8q - 14}{\sqrt{5}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{2}$

Proof of Theorem 2. From the Figure 2, Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6;

$$\begin{aligned}
M^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - II) &= \sum_{e \in E(Si_2C_3 - II)} deg_{ev} e^2 \\
&= 2x3^2 + 1x4^2 + (2p + 2q)x4^2 + (8p + 8q - 14)x5^2 \\
&\quad + (15pq - 13p - 13q + 11)x6^2 = 540pq - 236p - 236q + 80
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1^{\alpha ve}(Si_2C_3 - II) &= \sum_{v \in V(Si_2C_3 - II)} deg_{ve} v^2 \\
&= 2x2^2 + 1x3^2 + 2x3^2 + 2x4^2 + (4p + 4q - 6)x5^2 + (2p + 2q - 4)x6^2 \\
&\quad + (p - 3)x7^2 + (4p - 10)x8^2 + (10pq - 18p - 12q - 13)x9^2 \\
&= 810pq - 981p - 800q + 2067
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1^{\beta ve}(Si_2C_3 - II) &= \sum_{uv \in E(Si_2C_3 - II)} (deg_{ve} u + deg_{ve} v) \\
&= 2x5 + 1x10 + 2x7 + 2x9 + (2p + 2q - 4)x10 + (2p + 2q)x12 \\
&\quad + (2p + 2q - 2)x13 + (2p + 2q - 6)x14 + (2p + 2q - 6)x13 + 2x15 \\
&\quad + (2p + 2q - 8)x16 + 2x14 + (2p + 2q - 3)x16 + (2p + 2q - 5)x17 \\
&\quad + (15pq - 19p - 19q + 23)x18 = 270pq - 120p - 120q + 35
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_2^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - II) &= \sum_{uv \in E(Si_2C_3 - II)} deg_{ve} u deg_{ve} v = \\
&= 2x6 + 1x21 + 2x12 + 2x20 + (2p + 2q - 4)x25 + (2p + 2q)x35 \\
&\quad + (2p + 2q - 2)x42 + (2p + 2q - 6)x48 + (2p + 2q - 6)x40 + 2x56 \\
&\quad + (2p + 2q - 8)x64 + 2x49 + (2p + 2q - 3)x63 + (2p + 2q - 5)x72 \\
&\quad + (15pq - 19p - 19q + 23)x81 = 1215pq - 761p - 761q + 397
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R^{ve}(Si_2C_3 - II) &= \sum_{uv \in E(Si_2C_3 - II)} (deg_{ve} u deg_{ve} v)^{-1/2} \\
&= \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{12}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{20}} + \frac{2p+2q-4}{2} + \frac{2p+2q}{\sqrt{25}} + \frac{2p+2q-2}{\sqrt{35}} + \frac{2p+2q-2}{\sqrt{42}} \\
&+ \frac{2p+2q-4}{\sqrt{48}} + \frac{2p+2q-6}{\sqrt{40}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{56}} + \frac{2p+2q-8}{\sqrt{64}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{49}} + \frac{2p+2q-3}{\sqrt{63}} \\
&+ \frac{2p+2q-5}{\sqrt{72}} + \frac{15pq-19p-19q+23}{\sqrt{81}} \\
&= \frac{15pq-19p-19q+23}{9} + \frac{p+q-4}{2} + \frac{2p+2q-4}{5} + \frac{2p+2q}{\sqrt{35}} \\
&+ \frac{2p+2q-2}{\sqrt{42}} + \frac{2p+2q-4}{4\sqrt{3}} + \frac{2p+2q-6}{2\sqrt{10}} + \frac{2p+2q-3}{3\sqrt{7}} + \frac{2p+2q-5}{6\sqrt{2}} \\
&+ \frac{2}{7} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{21}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{14}} \\
R^{ev}(Si_2C_3 - II) &= \sum_{e \in E(Si_2C_3 - II)} deg_{ev} e^{-1/2} = \frac{15pq-13p-13q+11}{\sqrt{6}} + p+q \\
&+ \frac{8p+8q-14}{\sqrt{5}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{1}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

4. Conclusions

In this study we investigated the ev-degree and ve-degree topological properties of the twosilicon carbide structures: $Si_2C_3 - I$ and $Si_2C_3 - II$. The the ev-degree and ve-degree topological properties of other types of some chalcogenides are worth to study for future studies. Also mathematical properties of ev-degree and ve-degree topological indices are interesting studies for further studies.

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